

Some Preliminary Thoughts on a Biological Explanation for the Age Crime Curve

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This paper provides some preliminary thoughts about the structure of a biological explanation for the age crime curve. The age-crime curve is one of the most well established facts about the distribution of crime in the population (Farrington, 1986, Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). The relationship between age and crime was documented by Quetelet (1831/1984) in an examination of crime rates by age in France. He found that children under 10 rarely commit crimes. The level of crime then rises rapidly through the teen years until it peaks in young adulthood. At that time, the level of criminal activity drops off until few people in their 60s are found to be committing crimes. See Figure 1 for the age-crime curve found by plotting the number of arrests by age and gender in the United States for the eleven years from 1996 to 2006. It is clear that that peak level of offending for males is about four times the peak level of offending for females.

Figure 1: Total Arrests by Age and Gender for United States from 1996-2006 (Source National Incident Based Reporting Service - NIBRS)

There does not seem to be a satisfactory explanation for the age crime curve. Several criminologists discussed the age crime curve in the 1980s and 1990s, but a definitive causal explanation does not seem to have emerged (See Adams, 1997; Farrington, 1986; Gove, 1985; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). It would seem that this is a serious oversight. Without an adequate explanation for the causes of the population distribution of crime by age, it is difficult to identify the between individual differences in within-individual variation in crime. The cause of the age crime curve is a conceptual problem that must be solved if progress is to be made in a life course model of criminal activity.

There would appear to be several apparent “facts” that must be taken into consideration if one is to develop an understanding of the age crime curve. These facts are as follows,

- 1) the age crime curve is a population phenomenon and must be explained with population parameters

- 2) the shape of the age crime curve must be solely due to biological factors in the development of human beings

- 3) there is not one biological factor that can explain the age crime curve, and so a multiple factor solution with two or more factors is required

- 4) any theory that is developed should be parsimonious and require as few variables as possible

- 5) crime cannot be the only consideration for theory development, since crime is a social construct, and so analogous behaviors must be considered in any theory

6) analogous behaviors such as rule breaking and aggression are declining at the population level from birth, so whatever biological factor causes desistance in adulthood must have been operating from birth and causing desistance in children

7) the level of crime is directly related to the physical capacity needed to commit crimes

8) serious crimes are generally irrational activities that result from a lack of forethought by the person committing them and therefore crimes are inversely related to brain capacity

The justification for presenting these statements as “facts” is discussed below. This will be followed by the presentation of a two factor biological solution to the age crime curve that addresses these facts. It will be suggested that developmental changes in physical strength interact with developmental changes in the brain to create the age crime curve.

The Age Crime Curve as a Population Phenomenon

One factor that seems to have been somewhat overlooked in previous discussions is the fact that the age crime curve is a population phenomenon. The age crime phenomenon cannot be explained by looking solely at subgroups of the population. While there certainly are both between and within individual variation from highly criminal to noncriminal in the population, if one looks only at those who commit the greatest proportion of criminal behavior, the rest of the population would be ignored. Any theory that provides an explanation of the age crime curve must use population parameters in the explanation. Whatever is occurring that causes the age crime curve, it is occurring at

the population level for everyone in the population at approximately the same time, and this fact should be reflected in the population dynamics of developmental trajectories of the underlying factors that are proposed causes of the age crime curve.

The Age Crime Curve must be Due to Biological Causes

One of the primary theses of this paper is that the age crime curve must be due to biological factors. Gottfredson and Hirschi (1983) noted that the age-crime distribution pattern found by Quetelet (1831/1984) is found across all cultures, is found for both males and females, and also is seen for various crime types. Therefore, given that the age-crime curve is found across all cultures, for both sexes, and for various crime types, it is implausible that a sociological explanation is going to provide an adequate explanation of this phenomenon. If sociology cannot explain the age crime curve, then there must be some type of biological explanation.

This is not to say that sociology may not explain variation in the height of the age crime curve. Japan, for instance, has about a tenth of the crime found in the United States (Citation needed). It seems unlikely that this difference is completely due to biological differences, and so a sociological explanation is probably needed to explain some of the variation in total levels of crime between locales. However, after differences in level are accounted for, it is argued that the basic trajectory of the age crime curve is solely due to biological factors.

Given that a biological explanation is required, an analysis of population parameters for biological development will be used in the discussion that follows. It will

be assumed that whatever the biological factors that cause the age crime curve are, they are factors that change for the entire population at the same time that changes occur in the age crime curve. This perspective is built on the premise that rising tides lift all boats. The biological factors that cause acceleration and deceleration in crime are a direct result of population patterns of human ontogeny that occur for all people. Therefore, any biological factors proposed should affect criminals and non-criminals alike.

A Single Factor Biological Solution is Impossible

In searching for a biological explanation of the age crime curve, It appears that no one single biological factor will be adequate (cf. Gove, 1985). If the shape of the age crime curve shown in Figure 1 is examined, it is clear that the rapid acceleration in offending behavior seen in adolescence is followed by an almost equally rapid deceleration in offending behavior as the population enters early adulthood. There is no single biological factor that changes that quickly in the population, and so a single factor solution is not possible.

Solutions such as those proposed by Steinberg (2012), that suggest that brain development causes acceleration and declines in criminal activity are untenable, since the timing of these changes is unequal between individuals. Not every person suddenly develops a brain change exactly at the age of seventeen. There are also timing differences in these changes between males and females, and the age crime curves are the same for both sexes. Population level changes are not as rapid as the acceleration

and decline seen in the age crime curve. This means that an interaction between at least two biological factors is needed to explain the age crime pattern.

Any Theory that is Developed must be Parsimonious

Ockham had suggested that the simplest solution that fits the facts should be selected. Sober (1981) called this principle the "principle of parsimony." Any theory of the age crime curve should use as few variables as it possible. The age crime curve is a population process. Levels of crime are influenced by thousands of factors (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009). However, one should not need thousands of factors to explain the age crime curve. It should be possible, through logical examination of population biological dynamics, to find a few simple facts of human development that explain the age relationship between biological changes in the person and the population crime rate by age.

Any Proposed Solution Must Include Analogous Behaviors

Crime is a social construct. Crime is defined by the society that a person lives in. Things that are considered crimes vary by the age of the person. For instance, two year old children regularly bite, hit, and kick each other. These behaviors are not considered crimes for two year olds, and yet they would be considered crimes if an adult performed them. Therefore, any theory that attempts to explain the age crime curve must therefore consider analogous behaviors in the proposed solution. The two analogous behaviors used in this analysis are rule breaking and aggression. Crime is a violation of the rules of society. Extremely aggressive acts are sanctioned by the laws in most cultures, although

less aggressive acts are not. Crimes are serious violations of the rules, or serious acts of aggression.

Whatever is Causing Desistance from Crime in Adulthood is Causing Desistance in Children

Rule breaking and aggression decline from birth. Logically, if we consider the infant, we find that they do not know any rules other than those that are biologically imprinted. Children begin life as completely asocial beings. Therefore, the age of highest rule breaking is at age zero. We can consider children at age two, and there is good reason that we call them the terrible twos. They are self centered and generally are trying to get everyone else to do what they want, rather than doing what others want. With some exceptions, the population pattern is that children are taught to follow the rules as they age, and continue to be better at following the rules into adulthood.

Rule following behavior is increasing throughout the entire life course. Since crimes are simply formal rules, and rule breaking began to decline at birth, there must be something other than the cause of the decline in rule breaking that explains the apparent increase in rule breaking (criminal activity) during adolescence.

Similarly, aggression is declining from birth. Numerous studies have found this to be the case (See Nagin & Tremblay, 2005 for a review). Something is causing people to become less aggressive as they age. Again, since aggression is declining, something other than the cause of the decline in aggression must be causing the increased contact with the criminal justice system.

Crime Requires a Certain level of Physical Capacity

Adams (1997) suggested that physical strength is one factor that affects the level of crime with age. Crimes require a certain level of physical strength and agility, and this factor is changing over the life span. Therefore, it would be reasonable to assume that the amount of strength seen at different ages is directly related to the level of crime committed. Strength levels in the population increases in childhood, remain relatively stable, and then decreases in old age.

In the case of aggression, an increase in strength would explain why, even though overall levels of aggression decline as children age, they are seen to be committing more crimes of aggression in adolescent. Two 10 year olds hitting each other do little damage, and the police are generally not called to arrest them. Two seventeen year olds hitting each other can do considerable damage and may be charged with assault. Even though total levels of aggressive behavior are declining from age 10 to 17, there is more aggressive crime reported at age 17.

Crime is the Result of Inadequate Decision Making Ability

While it is possible to come up with exceptions, in general, crimes are highly irrational acts that result in little benefit for those committing them (cf. Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990). Moffitt (1993) suggested that criminals have "neurological deficits." Any explanation of the age crime curve must include the fact that decision making ability changes over the life course. In general decision making ability increases from birth to middle age, and then remains relatively constant until declines start to occur in old age.

It is also a fairly well established fact that brain development is another factor that affects the level of crime. From a bounded rationality perspective, the lack of cognitive ability found in children and adolescents makes them less able to make the decision to not commit crimes.

This premise is supported by authors such as Steinberg (2012), who argue that adolescents simply do not have the cognitive ability to make decisions like adults. The theory proposed here would suggest that Steinberg (2012) is only partially right however. He has argued that brain changes cause the increase in crime seen in adolescence, and this would not seem to be the case given that aggression and rule breaking are declining from birth. The argument that brain changes cause increases and decreases in crime also would seem to be false because these changes are not so sudden as to cause the rapid acceleration and deceleration in crime seen in adolescence. Therefore, it is assumed that brain development has a decelerating effect on rule breaking behavior over the life course.

A Two Factor Biological Solution to the Age Crime Curve

The question becomes, what is occurring, at the population level, in the biological development of the physical and mental capacities of the individual that would explain the crime and analogous behaviors that produce the age crime curve? In general, it would appear that two things are required for a crime to be committed, the physical capacity to commit the crime and a deficiency in the decision making capacity required to prevent the commission of the crime. If there is insufficient physical capacity, or the person has

sufficient common sense, crimes generally do not occur. The essence of the theory proposed below is that timing of developmental changes in physical strength and brain capacity cause the age crime curve.

The age crime curve can be shown to be due to developmental life course trajectories of physical strength and decision making capacity. It will be argued that there are three different phases in the life course development of humans that cause the age crime curve to have the distinctive shape that it has. The first phase is a childhood phase that runs from birth to about age eighteen as the child grows from an infant to an adult. Before about age ten, the children are generally too weak to commit most crimes, or society is unwilling to recognize the behavior as criminal. From about age 10 to 18, behaviors become increasingly serious as physical strength increases and activities are recognized as crimes. The second phase is a young to middle adult phase from 19 to 32 that is the result of ongoing brain development as people age, and the third phase is an older adult phase after age 33 that is the result of physical declines in old age. The basic two biological factor/three phase model is explained below, and then an attempt will be made to disprove this model.

Why Two Factors?

A two factor biological solution is proposed that combines two aspects of biological development, the ontogenetic trajectories of physical strength and brain development. If one starts with the premise that changes in physical strength and brain development are important factors in the etiology of crime, it is possible to construct a very simple two

factor solution that would explain the age crime curve using these two facets of biological development, physical development and brain development. While this solution may seem overly simplistic at first, the following theory would appear to be the only logical solution that fits all of the available facts.

Why Three Phases?

It will be suggested that there are three phases in the age crime curve that require separate explanations. This discussion will begin with an examination of the pattern of the age crime curves for males and females shown in Figure 2 below. The male and female age crime curves from Figure 1 the showed absolute numbers of offenses were converted to percentages of crimes by year of age for each gender to show how the percentage of offenses between genders changes with age.

Figure 2: Percentages of Crimes by Gender and Age (Males = 100%, Females = 100%, Source - NIBRS)

It appears that the age crime pattern seen in Figure 2 can be broken into three segments, birth to 18, 19 to 35, and 36 to 98. In the first segment, the crimes from birth to around age nine are almost completely absent from the model. There appears to be a threshold, below which, few crimes occur. From ages 10 to 19, there is a rapid linear acceleration in criminal behavior. In the second segment shown from 19 to 35, there is a rapid deceleration in crimes until about age 30 that eventually transforms into a more gradual deceleration from ages 31 to 40. It will be suggested that the overall crime pattern seen from 18 to 35 represents an inverted growth curve that is due to a single cause. In the third segment from ages 36 to 98, there is a moderate deceleration in criminal activity until no crimes are committed. In summary, it is proposed that there is an initial segment from birth to age 18, with few crimes occurring before age nine and an almost linear acceleration in crime from age 10 to 18. Then, there is a segment from age 19 to 35 that is an inverted growth curve with initially rapid and then slower declines in crime. Finally, there is a segment from 36 to 98 that represents a moderate deceleration in crime with few crimes committed after about age 65.

It will be argued that each of the three patterns seen in these three sections is caused by a different causal mechanism. The acceleration seen in the first section is caused primarily by increases in physical strength found over the first 18 years of life, the deceleration found in the second section is caused by adult brain development, and the deceleration in the third section is caused by physical declines seen after age 35. In

essence, it will be argued that the normal development of physical and mental capacities are the cause of the age crime curve.

A Look at Developmental Trajectories of Strength and Brain Capacity

First, the population age strength trajectory will be examined. This pattern is displayed in figure 3 below. In general, strength begins at a very low level at birth and climbs steadily until about age 20. It then remains fairly stable until about age 45, when strength starts to decline. If this is compared with the pattern seen in the age crime curve, it would appear that the increases in strength found from age ten to 20 closely mirror the increases in crime found during that age period. Similarly, the declines in strength seen from age 45 to 60 also mirror the declines in crime from ages 45 to 60. So far, it would appear that the strength curve matches the crime rates seen in the first and third section of the age crime curve.

Figure 3 – Physical Strength by Age

The second hypothesis is that the avoidance of criminal behavior requires a certain level of decision-making capacity. For the purposes of this discussion, it is suggested that the decision-making capacity of the brain starts at a low point and grows over the life course, eventually flattening out and then declining. A hypothetical approximation of the developmental trajectory of the growth of the decision-making capacity of the brain over the life course is shown in Figure 3. This model is supported by MRI studies that demonstrate that the brain’s functional ability is growing in capacity as people age. Functional capacity increases over most of the life course, but starts to decline in old age.

Figure 4: Hypothesized Growth of Decision Making Capacity with Age

If the level of rule breaking is inversely related to the brain's capacity to make decisions, then the level of rule breaking would follow a trajectory similar to that shown in figure 5. Rule breaking would be high in infancy and decline with age. If this proposition were followed exactly, it is assumed that at some point in old age, the level of rule breaking would start to increase again. This is not shown here and is not relevant to the discussion. Also, it should be noted that in the graph, rule breaking is shown to decrease to zero, which probably does not happen. The general idea that is presented is that, if rule breaking is inversely related to brain capacity, the pattern in Figure 4 should be seen in the level of rule breaking over the life course.

Figure 5: Hypothesized Rule Breaking Level with Age

The basic thesis of the argument for a two factor/ four phase biological developmental explanation for the age crime curve would be as shown in Table 1. From ages 0 to 10, no crime would be seen because strength is insufficient, even though rule breaking is high. From ages 10 to 18, as physical strength increased, and the increases in brain function and subsequent reductions in rule breaking and aggression do not keep pace, there is a rapid increase seen in crime. From 19 to 44, the physical strength levels remain fairly stable, and increases in brain function result in lower rates of crime. After age 45, the increases in brain function have essentially stopped and there may even be declines in brain functioning. However, the decline in strength beginning during this period results in reductions in crime.

Table 1: Calculated Slopes for Annual Changes in Crime Rate by Age

Age Range	Strength	Brain Function	Rule Breaking	Effect on Crime
0-9	Increasing	Increasing	Decreasing	No crime - Strength insufficient
9-18	Increasing	Increasing	Decreasing	Linear Increase in Crime
19-35	Stable	Increasing	Decreasing to Stable	Growth Curve Decline in

If the two graphs, rule breaking, and physical capacity are combined, the result under the curve would predict the level of criminal activity by age. From an examination of the graph in Figure 5, it becomes apparent that this hypothetical plot is very close in shape to the actual age-crime curve.

Figure 5: hypothetical Co-Plot of Strength and Rule Breaking

If the plot shown in Figure 5 is overlaid on the actual age crime curve, it becomes apparent that the two plots are nearly identical. Whatever is causing the age crime curve would appear to follow the general form of the hypothesized intersection of strength and brain capacity, assuming that there is a direct relationship between physical strength and crime and an inverse relationship between brain capacity and crime.

Figure 6: Hypothesized Age Crime Curve vs. 2005 UCR Age Crime Curve

Attempts to Disprove the Theory

One possible criticism of this theory is that it sounds like it states that strength causes crime. This is not the case. It is argued that lack of decision making capacity makes criminal activity more probable. Lack of strength makes crime less probable. As strength increases from birth, the inhibiting effect of no strength is disappearing. Since the inhibiting effect of brain capacity has not fully developed, crime occurs. There are three things affecting the age crime curve up until age 20. Physical capacity is increasing, rule breaking is decreasing, and there is a critical threshold below which, rule breaking behaviors are not considered crimes. These are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Intersection of Curves to Age 45

Conclusion

It seems entirely counter intuitive to think that crime is the result of human ontogeny. The traditional conception that crime is evil would suggest that criminals are not produced in the population in the normal course of human development. However, this theory proposes just that. The age crime curve would appear to be “caused” by a lag in brain development that is accompanied by changes in physical capacity to commit crimes. This two factor-four phase biological theory fits all of the requirements of a theory for the age crime curve. It uses population parameters, multiple biological factors, and it is parsimonious. The data fit the model almost perfectly, and so any other theory would need to provide a better fit, or more logical assumptions.

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